

Research Issues Related to the Visualization of Complex and Networked Systems

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Abstract—A number of research issues are discussed on how best to visualize performance and vulnerability in complex and distributed network systems. A powerful paradigm would be to convey information about a distributed network to a decision maker using natural attributes of display systems such as color, shape, and other variables. Future visualizations are hypothesized to enable decision makers to better understand complex visualizations so they can allocate scarce resources to protect their networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern day systems for the military and industry are becoming increasingly complex and distributed, yet poorly understood. Many such networks are synthesized in an *ad hoc* manner as modern computer equipment, network devices, and other technologies are synthesized in an unplanned mode. Associated with these advances are the problems introduced on how decision makers, commanders, and other key people have to deal with information about such networks. Important properties of distributed systems such as performance, vulnerability, delegation of authority and responsibility need to be quantified and not allocated in a random manner. Key players, at the constituent nodes of such networks, may have distributed knowledge and control over the entire network but constrained to limited inter-communication capabilities.

This paper will discuss issues on how to best portray information in a visual sense to key decision makers generated on complex displays to better understand attributes of the overall system. Present two dimensional (2D) display systems have to be better augmented to handle the increasing complexity of present visualization methods for decision makers. The rendering of information in such visualizations presents many new challenges. Some of the new methods to portray vulnerability and performance of complex networks are discussed. Paradigms to test for the efficacy of alternative display methodologies are presented. Some of the key points are how to synthesize visual renderings that optimize human performance in visual search tasks within complex scenarios? Performance may be objectively determined by the time to perform a visual

search task, presumably in minimum time with maximum (or 100%) accuracy.

Speed accuracy tradeoffs are inherent in the design of human-machine systems and such relationships must also occur as human operators interact with such an intricate apparatus. The visualization of complex and distributed networks requires a new paradigm to render key information to decision makers. The optimization of such display systems must take into account the fact that the attention of the operator must be managed in an effective manner. To better direct the attention of key players involved in such visual renderings includes managing the “pop out effect” that can be induced by proper development of the complex display. The “pop out effect” can alert decision makers to sudden dynamical changes in the network which should rapidly be discovered by this key individual. The use of displays with dimensionality above 2D provides a possible paradigm to help manipulate this attention of the decision maker. Other uses of advanced display technology, such as animation may also influence attention to key dynamical events occurring within the network.

Means to portray the performance of distributed and network systems will also be presented. The vulnerability of key constituent nodes can be envisioned as well as the flow characteristics of different temporal-spatial attributes [1-3] of such configurations in terms of flow capability through these dispersed entities. Alternative means of displaying capability and vulnerability of detached systems will be discussed that may help optimize human performance as decision makers interact with complex visual renderings both statically and dynamically for critical decision making tasks.

II. A POSSIBLE VISUALIZATION

Fig. (1) portrays a possible visualization for a decision maker on the status of a complex network. In this rendering, the color green means the flow rate is high, the yellow indicates a slower flow rate and the orange and red are yet slower flow rates. The advantage of this visualization is that the decision maker can immediately discern the geographical location of the areas of slow

and faster flow. The underlying presumption is that high flow rate is correlated with good performance. More congested areas probably reflect upon problematic regions.

Fig. (1) – Rendering a Complex System

III. PERFORMANCE/VULNERABILITY MEASURES

In [1,2] and a companion paper in this conference [3], methods are outlined on how to calculate performance and vulnerability of complex networks. These techniques provide a means to objectively quantify the issues of flow performance of distributed systems for decision makers. The next step is how to present this complex information in a manner which has utility to people who quickly have to assess a situation.

IV. A PARADIGM TO DISPLAY PERFORMANCE/VULNERABILITY

In Fig. (2) is portrayed a possible means of displaying both performance and vulnerability attributes of a complex network. To explain Fig. (2), the node or groups of nodes that

Legend

Performance:

Large flow rate (wide arrows, green color).

Slow flow rate (narrow arrows, red color).

Vulnerability:

Transparent ellipsoids. The larger the ellipsoid, the more vulnerable/sensitive.

Fig. (2) – A Possible Paradigm to Display both Performance and Vulnerability in a Complex Visual Display

Are considered to be more vulnerable (in an objective sense as determined in [1-3]) are enclosed within larger transparent ellipsoids. The less vulnerable nodes are encased with a smaller vulnerability ellipsoid. For flow performance between maximum and minimum overall flow conditions through the network, the white and blue areas of the arrows indicate the flow changes between these two extremes. Thus the decision maker can see which groups of nodes are vulnerable and the corresponding links that cause this vulnerability to occur.

Also a paradigm to attack a network can be obtained. The decision maker can see which groups of nodes have the highest vulnerability (encased in the largest transparent ellipsoid). The goal of the defender of the network would be to allocate resources to protect the most vulnerable node areas. Conversely the goal of the attacker would be to utilize his resources to attack certain groups of nodes based on their vulnerability ellipsoid sizes.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper discusses a number of issues related to the present and future methods being considered for display of complex visualizations. Important considerations such as visual search time, dimensionality of the display, and the most common methods of managing attention (shape, color, etc.) are elaborated upon. Several suggestions of possible display renderings are presented. Multi-objective performance data are presented in the hypothesized visualizations.

REFERENCES

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